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Test of thin-film samples

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the superconducting radio-frequency (SRF) performance of alternative materials to niobium for accelerator cavities. Using the Quadrupole Resonator (QPR) at Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB), four different Nb₃Sn and Nb-on-Cu samples, fabricated by various collaboration partners, were tested at cryogenic temperatures. The results showed that Nb₃Sn films from INFN Legnaro exhibited the best performance, with a low surface resistance (~25 nΩ at 4K) and strong flux expulsion. The STFC sample demonstrated lower uniformity and higher resistance (~90 nΩ), indicating contamination issues. Siegen University's Nb-on-Cu coating achieved excellent RF properties, confirming its readiness for application. In contrast, the HZB bronze-route Nb₃Sn-on-Cu sample suffered from stoichiometric inconsistencies and high surface resistance (~76 nΩ at 2K), requiring further process refinements. These findings provide crucial insights for optimizing alternative SRF material deposition techniques for future accelerator applications.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

This report presents the results of quality factor and surface resistance measurements for alternative superconducting radio-frequency (SRF) materials, focusing on Nb₃Sn and Nb-on-Cu coatings. The tests were conducted using the Quadrupole Resonator (QPR) at Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB) at cryogenic temperatures. The goal was to evaluate the viability of these materials for accelerator cavity applications.

Four samples, each produced by different collaboration partners, were tested:

Nb₃Sn on Nb (INFN Legnaro & STFC Daresbury)

- *Both samples exhibited nearly identical critical quench fields (~77 mT).*
- *The INFN sample showed superior surface resistance (~25 nΩ at 4K), whereas the STFC sample performed worse (~90 nΩ at 4K), likely due to non-uniformity and contamination.*
- *Cooling dynamics significantly impacted the INFN sample's performance, highlighting the importance of flux expulsion techniques.*

Nb-on-Cu (Siegen University)

- *A high-quality Nb film (~5 μm) was successfully deposited on Cu.*
- *The sample demonstrated an exceptionally high quench field (~260 mT) and low surface resistance (~20 nΩ at 2K).*
- *The study confirmed the importance of exceeding a threshold cool-down gradient (20 K/min) for optimal flux expulsion.*

Nb₃Sn on Nb-on-Cu (HZB via Bronze Route)

- *A novel bronze-route method was tested for Nb₃Sn deposition on a Nb-coated Cu substrate.*
- *Initial results indicated non-uniform stoichiometry and contamination, leading to a lower transition temperature (~15.5 K) and higher surface resistance (~76 nΩ at 2K).*
- *Further process refinements, such as improving homogeneity and phase purity, are necessary.*

Implications for Manufacturing

INFN's Nb₃Sn process is ready for application to accelerator cavities.

STFC's Nb₃Sn coatings require further optimization, particularly in contamination control.

Siegen's Nb-on-Cu deposition is fully developed and reliable.

The HZB bronze route for Nb₃Sn-on-Cu requires significant improvements before scaling up.

This study provides critical insights for advancing alternative SRF materials and optimizing their deposition methods for future accelerator applications.

1 Introduction

The optimization of deposition procedures of alternative SRF materials to Nb was the topic of previous work packages and deliverables. Deliverable 9.6 deals with the ultimate test prior to applying the procedure to the inside of accelerator cavities: The measurement of quality factor (surface resistance) vs accelerating gradient (magnetic field) on a dedicated flat sample at cryogenic temperatures and operating radio-frequencies. Such measurements were performed with the quadrupole resonator (QPR) at HZB. Since QPR measurements require significant preparation time, delicate and ultra-clean sample handling as well as 2 weeks of net measurement time at 1.8 K liquid Helium, only a limited number of tests can be performed in a given time. For I.Fast a total of four samples prepared in the labs of four different collaboration partners was selected and thoroughly tested. The results of these tests are presented below and their implication on the manufacturing process is discussed.

2 Tested samples

Since the beginning of I.Fast world-wide research focus in alternative SRF materials has shifted towards Nb₃Sn. Therefore, also for I.Fast main focus has been directed on Nb₃Sn deposition. Nb₃Sn samples were manufactured with the state-of-the-art DC magnetron sputtering techniques at INFN Legnaro and STFC Daresbury on a bulk Nb QPR substrate, respectively. Siegen University provided a Nb-on-Cu sample on a bulk copper QPR substrate which was measured at HZB and eventually processed to a Nb₃Sn on Cu sample via bronze route that was applied at HZB. This sample replaced the originally planned Nb₃Sn via ALD coated QPR from Saclay which was stalled due to the ongoing lack of suitable precursor materials for ALD deposition of Nb₃Sn.

2.1 Nb₃SN ON NB FABRICATED AT INFN LEGNARO AND AT STFC

Both, INFN and STFC optimized their magnetron sputtering techniques in recent years as described in detail in various previous publications and reports, see (Ghigo, Fracasso et al. 2025) and (Pira, Chyhrynets et al. 2019).

Here, we report the RF measurements of both samples in direct comparison of the two techniques applied to a Nb QPR sample substrate. It should be mentioned that the STFC substrate received significantly longer chemical etching resulting in a smoother initial surface of $R_z < 1\mu\text{m}$ compared to the INFN sample which had $R_z > 6\mu\text{m}$.

Figure 1: RF quench field vs sample temperature of INFN and STFC sample

Figure 2: Frequency shift vs sample temperature of INFN sample

Figure 3: STFC sample frequency shift vs sample temperature during monitored while warming up the sample

Figure 4: INFN sample surface resistance vs sample temperature

Figure 5: INFN sample, surface resistance vs field

Both samples – somewhat unexpectedly – exhibited an almost identical critical quench field, see Figure 1. This field can be extrapolated from the temperature dependence of the critical field which is different for both samples. Still they both yield extrapolated values $H_{sh}(T = 0 \text{ K}) = 77.2 - 77.9 \text{ mT}$. The critical temperature of the INFN sample was measured from the temperature dependence of the

QPR resonant frequency, see Figure 2, giving $T_c = 17.6-17.7$ K. This value is consistent with the value extracted from the H_{sh} measurement. For the STFC sample the situation is more complicated: The T_c measurement from frequency shift (Figure 3) yields 16.4 K while extrapolation from the quench field give 15.9 K. The reason for the inconsistency is most likely a non-uniform quality of the Nb_3Sn layer. The frequency method yields an average value of T_c over the entire illuminated sample surface, while the value obtained with the critical-field method is determined by the lowest transition temperature anywhere on the sample. Hence, the measurement indicates the presence of inhomogeneities or contaminations in the STFC sample that cause a local poor performance while the average performance is only slightly worse.

The penetration depth can be obtained by fitting the frequency vs temperature curve using Slater's theorem. For the INFN sample this yields 315 ± 24 nm which is in good agreement with the literature value. For the STFC sample the Slater fit does not converge. Like with the T_c measurements a possible explanation is a non-uniformity of the Nb_3Sn layer which causes the mean-free-path of the Cooper pairs to change with depth – which is not covered by the Slater formula.

The transition temperature has direct impact on the RF-surface resistance, the most important property of the film. In Figure 4 the surface resistance of the INFN sample at a constant peak field of 30 mT is plotted against temperature, in Figure 5 the surface resistance at 4 Kelvin (the atmospheric temperature of liquid Helium) is plotted against the peak RF magnetic field. All values were taken at 417 MHz where typically the residual resistance is in the same order of magnitude as the BCS resistance. The best surface resistance value achieved at 4 K was around 25 n Ω . Applied to an SRF cavity such a film would outperform a Nb bulk cavity at 1.8 K. The parameterization of the plots in Figure 4 and Figure 5 show a significant dependence of the surface resistance from the cool-down conditions. The initial cool-down starts from room temperature and liquid Helium is slowly filled into a bath cryostat housing the QPR. It suffers from significant local temperature gradients in particular between QPR pole shoes and sample surface. By this a characteristic “lensing” effect can take place that results in elevated flux trapping in the RF region of the sample and thus increased surface resistance (blue crosses in Figure 4). By thermal cycling (i.e. intermediately raising the sample temperature above T_c one can reduce the trapped flux or redistribute it in regions of the sample which carry lower RF magnetic field. It is also possible to fill the cryostat faster or slower than default which results in different levels of flux expulsion. In the QPR the best measurements were obtained after thermal cycling. Slow cool-down yields worse (higher) surface resistance values and is therefore counterproductive. Fast cool-down, however, as opposed to observations in cavities, does not necessarily reduce the trapped flux. Due to the peculiarities of the QPR geometry and the conduction cooling of the sample inside the QPR it is very likely that trapped flux can be minimized but not entirely eliminated. Therefore the true surface resistance values of the samples are likely even better than measured with the QPR.

The STFC sample exhibits a different surface resistance behaviour: Figure 6 shows the measured surface resistance at 20 mT and 416 MHz. While the performance at 1.8 K is almost the same as at 4 K the absolute values of 90 n Ω are significantly worse (higher) than for the INFN sample. This is very likely due to the contaminations or stoichiometric deviations that already led to the lower T_c of the sample. Also, cool-down dynamics have a much smaller relative and even absolute impact on the achieved surface resistance value: The STFC sample exhibited a variation of ~ 5 n Ω , while the spread

was over 30 nΩ for the INFN sample. The explanation for this behaviour is, again, contaminations on the surface of the STFC sample which prevent efficient flux expulsion during the Meissner transition of the sample resulting in 100% trapping independent of the cool-down conditions. Furthermore, the STFC sample exhibits an unexpected non-monotonic behaviour in surface resistance versus temperature curve, with a minimum at 3.2 K. The reason for this behaviour is unclear. One possible explanation is poor film adhesion in combination with a non-monotonous thermal conductivity of the Nb₃Sn film. The film also shows an unusually high surface resistance at 8 K. Fitting the data yields a too high BCS contribution. The reason for this could be incomplete coverage of the Nb substrate. The contribution of even small areas of exposed Nb to the surface resistance becomes dominant towards the transition temperature of Nb of 9.1 K leading to the measurement of increased surface values. This interpretation is consistent with the conclusions from the penetration depth measurement.

Figure 7 shows the surface resistance versus peak RF field measurement yielding stable surface resistance values around 95 nΩ up 30 mT overlaid by a mid-field Q-drop above 40mT and a slight low field Q-drop below 20 mT.

Figure 6: STFC sample surface resistance vs sample temperature at different cooldown velocities

Figure 7: STFC sample surface resistance vs peak field on sample at different cooldown velocities

2.2 NB ON CU FABRICATED AT SIEGEN UNIVERSITY

The Nb on Cu coating procedure was extensively developed and optimized in the ARIES project. It was performed on composite QPR samples consisting of a copper sample disc brazed into a QPR-sample matrix made from niobium. The original reason for using composite QPR-samples were (1) the necessity to minimize RF-heating in the coaxial gap between samples and resonator and (2) the consideration that a copper QPR-sample would have a too high thermal conductivity which compromises the calorimetric measurement principle of the QPR. For I.Fast the most successful coating procedure developed at Siegen university (Sezgin, Diaz-Palacio et al. 2022) was applied to a full copper QPR-sample on which also the side surfaces of the QPR sample cylinder had to be coated. It was found that calorimetry also works for high RRR copper samples. As a by-product, adapting the coating technique to also cover vertical surfaces is an important step towards coating curved surfaces such as in cavities.

Figure 8: Siegen Nb-on-Cu RF quench field vs sample temperature

Figure 9: Siegen Nb-on-Cu frequency vs sample temperature

Figure 10: Siegen Nb-on-Cu sample surface resistance vs cooldown speed through T_c at 4 K

Figure 11: Siegen Nb-on-Cu sample surface resistance vs cooldown speed through T_c at 2 K

A $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ thick Nb film was prepared on a bulk copper substrate and measured with QPR: Figure 8 shows the RF quench field as a function of the squared temperature. The extrapolation to 0 K reveals a very high quench field of 260 mT.

The critical temperature was 9.3 K, also suggesting very good film quality. The frequency shift measurement (Figure 9) confirms the T_c value, however, there was not enough data to perform the fit of the penetration depth.

Figure 10 shows the surface resistance values at 4 K, obtained for different cool-down speed values, i.e. the temporal temperature gradient during the transition through T_c . Like in bulk Nb cavities there is a threshold gradient that should be exceeded in order to ensure maximum flux expulsion. It is 20 K/min for the Siegen sample. To our knowledge the existence of the threshold gradient has never been demonstrated in an Nb film before. The surface resistance values at 2 K and 10 mT are shown in Figure 11. The best value obtained was 20 n Ω which is achieved when exceeding the threshold cool-down gradient of 20 K/min. In

Figure 12 shows the surface resistance versus sample temperature at 2 K and 20 mT after the initial cool-down. The monotonous increase is consistent with the expected behavior of the BCS resistance. Finally, Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the surface resistance vs peak field measurements at 4 K and

2 K, respectively. Overall, it can be concluded that the film quality was very good and the coating was sufficiently homogeneous. Besides, it was demonstrated that the calorimetric measurement principle also works with copper substrates despite its much larger thermal conductivity compared to niobium.

Figure 12: Siegen Nb-on-Cu sample, surface resistance vs sample temperature at 20 mT after initial cooldown

Figure 13: Siegen Nb-on-Cu surface resistance vs peak field on sample at 4 K

Figure 14: Siegen sample surface resistance vs peak field on sample at 2 K

2.3 Nb₃Sn ON Nb ON CU FABRICATED AT HZB VIA BRONZE ROUTE

With the establishment of a successful Nb on Cu coating procedure for QPR samples at Siegen a new pathway for Nb₃Sn production opened up, that was further pursued at HZB. The bronze route is a method to synthesize Nb₃Sn thin films at 700 °C on Cu substrates. The specific procedure was not yet published which is why this is done in this report: It involves a diffusion reaction between niobium and an electrochemically deposited bronze alloy to form Nb₃Sn. The copper is expelled from the Nb₃Sn during the reaction. Afterwards the copper is etched away from the top, leaving a pure Nb₃Sn layer behind.

The process utilized the HiPIMS coated Nb-on-Cu sample prepared by Siegen university described in section 2.2. A bronze precursor layer was electroplated onto the Nb-coated substrate, serving as

Figure 15: Schematic diagram of preparing Nb₃Sn by bronze route

Figure 16: Preparation process of Cu-based Nb₃Sn QPR sample by bronze route

the Sn source for Nb₃Sn formation. Next, 700°C heat treatment was performed to grow the superconducting Nb₃Sn phase, see Figure 15 and Figure 16. Finally, the bronze on the surface was removed by chemical etching to obtain the final Cu-based Nb₃Sn thin film.

At present, the RF test of the first bronze QPR sample has been completed, and the surface resistance, critical temperature and critical magnetic field have been evaluated. The measurement series is shown in Figure 17 to Figure 22. R_s is measured to be about 76 nΩ at 2 K and 5 mT. The transition temperature and width of Nb₃Sn is about 15.5 K. A large width of the transition of 4K suggests an early onset of flux penetration and/or a non-uniform film quality with off-stoichiometric areas of the film surface. It is known, that stoichiometry deviations in Nb₃Sn bias both T_c and the maximum RF field which is likely to have occurred in the sample. The surface resistance is fairly stable against variations of the cool-down speed which suggests domination of BCS losses – very likely caused by poor film quality. So, the first Nb₃Sn/Cu QPR sample coating quality is not very good. Problems such as low Sn content, surface defects and contamination, and copper exposure have been found, which will guide further process improvements in the future.

Figure 17: Frequency vs Temperature of Nb₃Sn sample prepared by the bronze route

Figure 18: Surface resistance at different cool-down speed values

Figure 19: Surface resistance vs peak field on sample at different cool-down velocities

Figure 20: Dependence of surface resistance at 4 K on cool-down speed at different field levels

Figure 21: Dependence of surface resistance at 4 K on peak RF field at different cool-down velocities

Figure 22: Temperature dependence of surface resistance at 10 mT

3 Implication of results on manufacturing procedure

The QPR measurements of samples have yielded important information on the true RF performance of Nb₃Sn films produced by partners within the I.Fast collaboration. While the INFN facility has delivered sufficient film quality to take the next step towards applying the method on a cavity, STFC needs to improve the coating parameters further – most likely a full bake-out of the coating system will bring significant improvements here. The Nb coating procedure at Siegen reliably delivers decent Nb-on-Cu coatings and can be considered fully developed. The bronze route at HZB needs further improvement in particular with respect to increasing homogeneity and phase pureness.

4 References

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